

“RBP-ReguNet”

Deliverable 5.1

PRCP: DC personal research career development plan

PROJECT INFORMATION

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CONTACT	info@rbp-regunet.eu

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

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LIST OF BENEFICIARIES AND PARTNER ORGANIZATIONS

ORGANIZATION	COUNTRY	ROLE	NAME	ACADEMY
USC	SPAIN	C	Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo	academy
USC	SPAIN	B	Dr. Marta Varela Rey	academy
IC	FRANCE	B	Prof. Stephan Vagner	academy
CRG	SPAIN	B	Prof. Fátima Gebauer	academy
CRG	SPAIN	B	Prof. Juan Valcárcel	academy
SANQ	NETHERLANDS	B	Prof. Monika Wolkers	academy
IMMAG	ITALY	B	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	non-acade
UNITN	ITALY	B	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	academy
UMIL	ITALY	B	Prof. Pierfausto Seneci	academy
EMBL	GERMANY	B	Prof. Mathias Hentze	academy
MRC-CVR	UK	AP	Prof. Alfredo Castello	academy
KAERTOR	SPAIN	AP	Prof. Mabel Loza	non-acade
RIBONEX	FRANCE	AP	Dr. Steven Powell	non-acade
CNR	ITALY	AP	Dr. Daniela Arosio	academy
UPSACLAY	FRANCE	AP-B		academy
UPF	SPAIN	AP-B		academy
UVA	NETHERLANDS	AP-B		academy

GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

DC	Doctoral Candidate
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions
PCDP	Personal Career Development Plan
PRCP	Personal Research Career Plan
SB	Supervisory Board
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, and Timely
TDC	Training/Doctoral Studies Committee

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

RBP-ReguNet project is designed to harness recent discoveries for the identification of druggable targets across a spectrum of untreated diseases, encompassing cancer, neurological disorders, liver diseases, and infectious diseases. Our main aspiration within RBP-ReguNet is to establish an advanced training program rooted in basic research yet bearing a significant impact on clinical translation. This program will deliver comprehensive multidisciplinary scientific training, spanning computational, structural, molecular, and cellular biology to medicinal chemistry and pharmacological screening, fostering the next generation of European researchers in an intersectoral setting. This environment aims to propel ambitious and high-impact research focused on developing new therapies based on RBP biology.

The main goal of RBP-ReguNet is to mentor eleven young scientists through individual research projects within the field of gene expression control. We aim to translate fundamental discoveries into actionable druggable targets, employing a multidisciplinary and intersectoral strategy that exposes the researchers to diverse methodologies, disciplines, and knowledge contributed by each partner.

The specific training in the main laboratories, combined with secondments in complementary disciplines in host laboratories as well as a set of research and inter-sectoral training will provide the DCs with a deep understanding of their field of research, while at the same time attaining a broad perspective on different career paths. DCs will receive a robust package of transversal and transferable skills, including communication, writing, data management, entrepreneurship and intellectual property rights (IPR) protection, suited to both academic and non-academic careers.

In the initial months of recruitment, researchers have formulated a Personal Career Development Plan (PCDP) in collaboration with the main supervisor, co-supervisor, and mentors, under the guidance of the Training/Doctoral Studies Committee. To ensure clarity and achievability of goals, the PCDP should adhere to SMART guidelines (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, and Timely), drawing inspiration from the Vitae Researcher Development Framework¹. This framework outlines the extensive knowledge, intellectual abilities, techniques, and professional standards required for research, as well as the personal qualities, knowledge, and skills necessary for collaboration and ensuring the broader impact of research. The PCDP should further integrate the scientific project with well-defined research objectives and training activities, will be updated every 12 months by the Training/Doctoral Studies Committee, considering the evolving needs and aspirations of the researchers.

¹ [The Vitae Researcher Development Framework — Vitae Website](#)

2. OBJECTIVE

The goal of developing a comprehensive Personal Career Development Plan (PCDP) for each of the eleven doctoral candidates within the project is to provide a structured framework that aligns individual career aspirations with the overarching objectives of the research program. The PCDP includes a short-term (1-2 years) and a long term (over 5 years) version and should cover essential aspects of the research career path of the DCs:

1. Research results
2. Research skills and techniques to be acquired by the fellow
3. Research management
4. Communication skills
5. Teaching, supervision, or mentoring
6. Networking
7. Other transferable skills with professional relevance for the DC

3. SUPERVISION ARRANGEMENTS

3.1. Quality of the supervision

Each of the 11 DCs hired through RBP-ReguNet will conduct their PhD projects in the laboratories of leading researchers in Europe, across a range of disciplines including computational biology, structural biology, molecular and cellular biology, medicinal chemistry, drug discovery, oncology, gastroenterology, neurology, immunology, and virology. All supervisors have internationally acknowledged expertise in their research field and have extensive supervision experience of PhD, Postdocs and MSc students and track record with European networks. They will provide research support, career development counselling, mentorship and ensure personal well-being of students, while keeping a clear regular communication to monitor progress.

3.2. Monitoring

All the DCs will have a personalized PhD committee comprising their main supervisor, a co-supervisor from the RBP-ReguNet network and mentors, including one from the academic sector and one from the non-academic sector (Table 1).

Table 1. Doctoral Candidates and their designated supervisors and mentors.

DC NO	NAME	SUPERVISOR	CO-SUPERVISOR	ACADEMIC MENTOR	INDUSTRIAL MENTOR	DOCTORAL DEGREE AWARD
DC1	Yuqing Wang	Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo	Dr. Marta Varela Rey	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	Prof. Mabel Loza	USC
DC2	Sofia Perdikari	Dr. Marta Varela Rey	Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo	Prof. Alfredo Castello	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	USC
DC3	Sidhant Kalia	Prof. Stephan Vagner	Prof. Fátima Gebauer	Prof. Mathias Hentze	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	UPSACLAY
DC4	Dominika Zurkowska	Prof. Fátima Gebauer	Prof. Mathias Hentze	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	Dr. Steven Powell	UPF
DC5	Giulia Granata	Prof. Juan Valcárcel	Prof. Stephan Vagner	Prof. Mathias Hentze	Prof. Mabel Loza	UPF
DC6	Zan Hozjan	Prof. Monika Wolkers	Prof. Mathias Hentze	Prof. Fátima Gebauer	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	UVA
DC7	Namah Raut	Prof. Alfredo Castello	Prof. Mathias Hentze	Prof. Juan Valcárcel	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	UGLASGOW
DC8	Amina Adam	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo	Dr. Steven Powell	UNITN
DC9	Marina Benitez Ramos	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo	Prof. Stephan Vagner	Prof. Mabel Loza	UNITN
DC10	Salma Hesse	Prof. Pierfausto Seneci	Dr. Daniela Arosio	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	Prof. Mabel Loza	UMIL
DC11	Antonio Biancolella	Prof. Mathias Hentze	Prof. Juan Valcárcel	Prof. Alfredo Castello	Dr. Steven Powell	EMBL

The main supervisor will normally have weekly personal meeting with DCs and will be responsible for all aspects of their training. The co-supervisors and mentors will meet with the DCs during network-wide activities or meetings and will predominantly be advising the DCs on career choices and complementary transferable skills.

The DCs will have to submit monthly reports to their main supervisor whilst on secondments as well as meetings through videoconferencing. The Training/Doctoral studies Committee (TDC) will outline and analyse the PCDP with its defined training plan, objectives and milestones that will be evaluated and updated every 12 months. In addition, some of the DCs will have the benefit of a second local Thesis Advisory Committee with input from independent advisers (section 1.3.1 of the GA). Corrective actions will be taken to mitigate any adverse event during the training (Risk Management, Section 3.1.10 of the GA).

The TDC will also generate an annual summary report of the progress of each DC (achievements in terms of patents/publications, outreach activities, skills courses and secondments) that will be presented to the SB and EAB at their annual meeting to monitor the progress of the network training objectives as a whole and decide on corrective measures if required. The report will constitute the **Deliverable 5.2: Annual DC reports: local training for all DCs and Network-training activities**

4. TRAINING

4.1. Local

Each DC fellow will work on an individual research project (details in section 3.1.4 of the GA), and all DCs will be enrolled in official PhD doctoral programs, either (i) at their host beneficiary (where the beneficiary can award PhD title, USC, MRC-CVR, EMBL, UNITN, UMIL), (ii) at local universities when the recipient cannot award a PhD degree but has an agreement with associated universities (e.g. UPF in the case of CRG fellows, UniTN in the case of IMMAGINA, UvA for SANQUIN, and UPSaclay in the case of IC). Each DC will be expected to accumulate 30 ECTS credits in core research skills and transferable skills for their doctoral awards.

Internal training activities: DCs will participate in lab meetings, journal clubs and institutional seminars that are available in each participating institution, where the DCs will be exposed to latest results and ideas from fellow work colleagues and leading scientists, widening their background scientific knowledge and breadth of their own research projects.

Outreach and public engagement: In addition to planned outreach activities planned (section 2.3.1 of the GA), DCs will also participate in outreach activities at the institutional level (open days, etc.) or local community level, e.g., Cancer Awareness Month.

4.2. Network Training courses

All participating scientists and DCs will contribute to the meetings and training events, and the hosting of events will rotate between beneficiaries to maximise mobility of DCs. Two scientific network meetings will be held (CRG, IC), where DCs will give short talks about their individual projects and results, followed by discussion, and feedback on experimental plans and secondments. This will provide excellent training for their presentation and communication skills.

4.2.1. Workshops

Three integrative workshops, organized and conveyed by all supervisors at 4 locations (USC, EMBL, and UNITN), will cover fundamental aspects of the research program in RBP-ReguNet (pre-clinical disease models, early drug discovery pipeline, high throughput technologies, etc.).

	WORKSHOP	LEAD	MONTH	VENUE
W1	Preclinical disease models & advanced monitoring technologies	USC	18	online
W2	High throughput genomics technologies	EMBL	24-30	EMBL (Heidelberg, Germany)
W3	Early drug discovery pipeline	UNITN	40-42	UNITN (Trento, Italy)

4.2.2. Courses on transferable skills

We will offer five one-day courses designed to enhance the transversal skills and competences of Doctoral Candidates (DCs). These courses are integral to the career

development plan, aiming to integrate skilled talent into both the scientific community and society at large. These courses are designed to broaden and deepen research skills such as leadership, scientific writing, or tech transfer.

	CTS	HOST	MONTH	VENUE
CTS1	Core communication skills, time, and project management	USC	14	USC (Santiago de Compostela, Spain)
CTS2	Becoming a Scientific Writer – Putting Why before How	USC	14	USC (Santiago de Compostela, Spain)
CTS3	Beyond the Bench Career development for scientists: industry	EMBL	24	EMBL (Heidelberg, Germany)
CTS4	Crash Course on protection and valorisation of Intellectual Property	UNITN	40	UNITN (Trento, Italy)
CTS5	Entrepreneurship & Company Management	UNITN	40	UNITN (Trento, Italy)

4.2.3. International Symposium/Conference

Two international conferences will be organized (CRG and IC), covering the main aspects of RBP biology and target drug discovery, where the DCs will attend lectures and seminars by top experts in the field. The DCs will have the opportunity to present and discuss their work in dedicated oral sessions.

Led by UNITN, the consortium has already submitted a formal proposal to host the FASEB (Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology) international conference in 2025. FASEB is a federation of scientific societies that advances health and well-being by promoting research and education in biological and biomedical sciences. The conference provides a global platform that will benefit the visibility of the project's research achievements to attract potential collaborators and industry stakeholders. Hosting such a prestigious event shall increase networking opportunities, facilitate knowledge exchange, and strengthen our project's credibility within the scientific community.

After each network event, DCs and PIs will be asked to fill in questionnaires to measure effectiveness of training and identify improvement areas for future meetings.

4.3. Secondments

The DCs will have international secondments for about 3-8 months in 1-2 laboratories of beneficiaries to stimulate their exposure to European scientific and cultural diversity, with a special emphasis on a laboratory with a different discipline expertise (section 3.1.4 of the GA). The **Deliverable 5.3: DC reports: Secondments and collaborations** will summarize all planned and completed secondments during the project.

5. THE PERSONAL CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLANS

All PCDP should follow a basic template, agreed upon and included as an Annex to this document and to the Consortium Agreement. It should be designed together with his/her personal supervisor and co-supervisor and assisted by the Training and Doctoral Committee (TDC).

The PCDP should comprise the DCs training, career development needs, scientific project with well-defined research objectives and training activities, including the timeline for the secondments to other institutions.

The compiled plans should include the following sections:

1. Long-term career objectives (over 5 years) including long term goals and research activities/training required to attain these goals.
2. Short-term objectives (1-2 years) including anticipated research results (in terms of publications or events participation), research skills and techniques, plans for fellowship or funding applications, beyond research professional skills training, and anticipated networking activities.

The daily supervision of the progress of the individual DC projects will be the responsibility of the main supervisor with the assistance of the group co-supervisors, who will ensure the continued education of the DC and will make regular assessments of the achievements and training progress.

As previously stated, the DCs will give annual written reports on their activities and milestones achieved to the TDC for evaluation of the overall progress. The TDC will give regular feedback to the DCs, on their reports and presentations, which will guide the development and continuous adaptation of DC training plans if needed. The DCs will also have to follow the relevant structured training of their specific PhD programs at their host universities and will update the PCDP to document these activities.

At the end of each individual project, all DCs will develop with their supervisors and co-supervisors an updated Final Year PCDP.

6. DEVIATIONS

There are no detected deviations related to the present deliverable.

7. ANNEXES

7.1. Personal Career Development Plan Template

The agreed template for the Career Development Plan was provided by the Coordinator to guide the supervisors and DCs in compiling the personal plans for the fellows. The template is based on the EU Template² and is also annexed to the Consortium Agreement.

7.2. Vitae Researcher Development Framework (RDF)

The framework describes the knowledge, behaviour, and attributes of successful researchers³.

7.3. DCs' Personal Career Development Plans

² [PCDP EU HE template](#)

³ [About the Vitae Researcher Development Framework — Vitae Website](#)

ANNEX I

Personal Career Development Plan Template

Personal Career Development Plan

Host: Choose an item.
Doctoral Candidate Number: Choose an item.

Date: Click or tap to enter a date.
Doc. Version: 1.0

PROJECT INFORMATION

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER	101073094
PROJECT FULL TITLE	RBP-ReguNET – Deconstructing and Rewiring RNA-RBP regulatory networks
PROJECT ACRONYM	RBP-ReguNet
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START DATE OF THE PROJECT	1/3/2022
DURATION (MONTHS)	48
CALL IDENTIFIER	HORIZON-MSCA-DN-2021
PROJECT WEBSITE	www.rbp-regunet.eu

PERSONAL CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLAN	
HOST/BENEFICIARY	Choose an item.
DEPARTMENT/AREA	
SUPERVISOR NAME	
NETWORK CO-SUPERVISOR NAME	
MENTOR NAME (IF DEFINED)	
DOCTORAL CANDIDATE NUMBER	Choose an item.
DOCTORAL CANDIDATE NAME	

The PCDP will be aligned with SMART guidelines (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Timely), and will be informed by the [Vitae Researcher Development Framework](#), which sets out the wide-ranging knowledge, intellectual abilities, techniques, and professional standards expected to do research, as well as the personal qualities, knowledge and skills to work with others and ensure the wider impact of research.

The PCDP will integrate the scientific project with well-defined research objectives and training activities, including the timeline for the secondments to other institutions that will be defined within the first month of recruitment, and updated every six months by the Training/Doctoral studies Committee accordingly to the DC needs and aspirations.

The DCs will also have to follow the relevant structured training of their specific PhD programs at their host universities and will update the PCDP to document these activities.

1. Brief overview of research project and major accomplishments expected

Half page should be sufficient.

2. Long-term Career Objectives (over 5 years)

Goals

What further research activity or other training is needed to attain these goals?

Secondments?

3. Short-term Career Objectives (1-2 years)

3.1.1. Research results

These should give an overview of the main direct results obtained as a consequence of the research carried out during the training period. It may include publications, conference, workshop attendance, courses, and /or seminar presentations, patents etc. This will vary according to the area of research and the type of results most common to each field. The information at this level should be general since the career development plan does not strictly constitute a report on the scientific results achieved.

3.1.2. Research Skills and techniques acquired.

Competence in experimental design, quantitative and qualitative methods, relevant research methodologies, data capture, statistics, analytical skills.

Original, independent, and critical thinking.

Critical analysis and evaluation of one's findings and those of others.

Acquisition of new expertise in areas and techniques related to the researcher's field and adequate understanding their appropriate application.

Foresight and technology transfer, grasp of ethics and appreciation of IPPR.

3.1.3. Research management.

Ability to successfully identify and secure sources of funding for personal and team research as appropriate.

Project management skills relating to proposals and tenders work programming, supervision, deadlines and delivery, negotiation with funders, financial planning, and resource management.

Skills appropriate to working with others and in teams and in teambuilding.

3.1.4. Communication skills.

Personal presentation skills, poster presentations, skills in report writing and preparing academic papers and books.

To be able to defend research outcomes at seminars, conferences, etc.

Contribute to promote public understanding of one's own field.

3.1.5. Other professional training (course work, teaching activity):

Involvement in teaching, supervision, or mentoring.

3.1.6. Anticipated networking opportunities.

Develop/maintain co-operative networks and working relationships as appropriate with

supervisor/peers/colleagues within the institution and the wider research community

3.1.7. Other activities (community, etc.) with professional relevance.

Issues related with career management, including transferable skills, management of own career progression, ways to develop employability, awareness of what potential employers are looking for when considering CV applications etc.

X

Supervisor

X

Doctoral Candidate

ANNEX II

Vitae Researcher Development Framework (RDF)

The framework describes the knowledge, behaviour, and attributes of successful researchers

ANNEX II

DCs' Personal Career Development Plans